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Sliding Mode Control for a Quadrotor Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

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Abstract- In this article the sliding mode controller is applied for a small unmanned helicopter called quadrotor. The dynamic model is established considering various physical phenomena that can influence its dynamic behavior. Subsequently, backstepping controller is designed. Its job is to generate commands to the four rotors. The objective is to drive the quadrotor to track desired Cartesian positions and desired orientation. The proposed controller is based on the Lyapunov stability. This control technique was checked in simulation and has given good performance.

Keywords: Quadrotor UAV, Newton-Euler Formalism, Sliding Mode Controller, Tracking Trajectory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the use and development of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have been grown strongly. UAVs are becoming very popular and commercial military and academic platform. As an UAV, quadrotors are very attractive because they have excellent characteristics, such as the vertical take-off and landing ability, hovering, small size, higher manoeuvrability, low cost, etc. They flight with low speed and less distance, but they have the aptitude to hover near a specific object, and are suitable for missions that do not require high speed.

The selection of the suitable control technique for a quadrotor UAV is challenging for both indoor and outdoor environment; because of its under-actuated property, coupling between translational and rotational dynamics and its inherent nonlinearity. Authors in literature have proposed many control techniques for this class of systems. J. C. V. Junior et al in [1] have used PID controller to stabilize roll and pitch movements. However they came up with a conclusion that linear control cannot fulfil the requirements under some conditions. Other attempts for the quadrotor control were made based on feedback linearization (FL) [2, 3]. This technique is restricted for some applications because of its lack of precision. In [4], authors tackled the robustness against uncertainties. They concluded that FL is not a robust technique and sensitive to sensor noise. Hence, sliding mode control (SMC) performed well in presence of sensor noise.

This paper deals with the control of the quadrotor system based on SMC. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In section II, the dynamic model of the quadrotor is developed according to Newton-Euler formalism. Based on this nonlinear model, we design

in section III, the inputs lows of the SMC. Some simulation results are demonstrated in section IV, allowing the analysis of the proposed controller performance. Finally, we give a conclusion in section V.

2. DYNAC MODEL

The quadrotor, like it is shown in the Figure 1 is a helicopter configuration with four rotors in cross form. Reason for which, X4-flyer is a simple strongly significant name. We consider that the structure is rigid. Only the propellers speeds are changeable [5].

The dynamic model of X4-flyer is a system of equations describing its attitude and position in space, which are primarily those of a rigid body in rotation with six degrees of freedom at four inputs. The inputs represent the angular velocities of the four rotors. The motion study of such a body (position, orientation, speed and angular velocity) is reduced to study the movement of its center of gravity and its orientation with respect to an inertial reference frame. From where the need of associating a mobile frame with the solid to be studied, i.e. it follows instantaneously its movements (Figure 1).

Figure 1 X4-flyer structure.

The transformation between the two frames is given by the matrix (1):

$${}^I_B R = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta \cos \psi & \sin \phi \sin \theta \cos \psi - \cos \phi \sin \psi & \cos \phi \sin \theta \cos \psi + \sin \phi \sin \psi \\ \cos \theta \sin \psi & \sin \phi \sin \theta \sin \psi + \cos \phi \cos \psi & \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin \psi - \sin \phi \cos \psi \\ -\sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \theta & \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Unlike the classical helicopter which needs for the tail rotor, X4-flyer dynamic exploits the configuration of contrary pairs senses. If the rear and front propellers turn clockwise, the right and left ones rotate counter-clockwise.

While it is convenient to have the equations of the linear movement in the E frame, the equations of the rotational movement are useful in B frame, so that we can express rotations around the center of gravity of the vehicle. The system equations are provided using Newton-Euler formalism (1). $\xi = [x \ y \ z]^T$ is the translational movement

vector. $\Omega = [\Omega_x \ \Omega_y \ \Omega_z]^T$ contains the angular speeds. m is the X4-flyer mass while $I = \text{diag}[I_x \ I_y \ I_z]$ is its inertia matrix.

$$\begin{cases} m\ddot{\xi} = F_T - F_D - F_G \\ I\dot{\Omega} = \tau_{\phi,\theta,\psi} - \tau_a - \tau_g \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where F_T and $\tau_{\phi,\theta,\psi}$ are the force and the torque generated by the propellers. F_D and τ_a are the aerodynamic effects acting on the vehicle. F_G and τ_g are the gravity force and the gyroscopic effect, respectively, they can be expressed according to ω_i (refer to previous works for more details). $2l$ is the distance between two rotors of the same branch.

From (1) we have:

$$\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -s\theta \\ 0 & c\phi & c\theta s\phi \\ 0 & -s\phi & c\phi c\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Suppose that it is about small angles, thus we can assimilate the vector Ω to

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} & \dot{\theta} & \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix}^T.$$

The dynamic model of the X4-flyer is then given by the system (4):

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{x} = \frac{k_F}{m} \left[(c\phi s\theta c\psi + s\phi s\psi)(\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) - k_{dx} \dot{x} \right] \\ \ddot{y} = \frac{k_F}{m} \left[(c\phi s\theta s\psi - s\phi c\psi)(\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) - k_{dy} \dot{y} \right] \\ \ddot{z} = \frac{k_F}{m} \left[c\phi c\theta (\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) - k_{dz} \dot{z} - mg \right] \\ \ddot{\phi} = \frac{1}{I_x} \left[(I_y - I_z) \dot{\theta} \dot{\psi} + l.k_F (\omega_4^2 - \omega_2^2) - k_{d\phi} \dot{\phi}^2 - I_r \bar{\Omega} \dot{\theta} \right] \\ \ddot{\theta} = \frac{1}{I_y} \left[(I_z - I_x) \dot{\phi} \dot{\psi} + l.k_F (\omega_3^2 - \omega_1^2) - k_{d\theta} \dot{\theta}^2 + I_r \bar{\Omega} \dot{\phi} \right] \\ \ddot{\psi} = \frac{1}{I_z} \left[(I_x - I_y) \dot{\phi} \dot{\psi} + k_M (-\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 - \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) - k_{d\psi} \dot{\psi}^2 \right] \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where k_F , k_M are the lift and moment coefficients. $[k_{dx} \ k_{dy} \ k_{dz}]^T$ and $[k_{d\phi} \ k_{d\theta} \ k_{d\psi}]^T$ are the translational and rotational drag coefficients, and $\bar{\Omega} = -\Omega_1 + \Omega_2 - \Omega_3 + \Omega_4$

It is major to note that (5) are the control inputs:

$$\begin{cases} U_z = k_F (\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 + \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) \\ U_\phi = l.k_F (\omega_4^2 - \omega_2^2) \\ U_\theta = l.k_F (\omega_3^2 - \omega_1^2) \\ U_\psi = k_M (-\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2 - \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

3. CONTROL DESIGN

The X4-flyer is an under actuated system with four inputs vs six outputs, and strongly coupled. So, it is important to introduce virtual inputs based like in (6), to get the desired ϕ and θ angles.

$$\begin{cases} U_x = (c\phi s\theta c\psi + s\phi s\psi) \\ U_y = (c\phi s\theta s\psi - s\phi c\psi) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The control scheme recommended is then, based on two cascade loops. According to the desired values x_d and y_d , the outer control loop calculates desired roll and pitch angles (ϕ^d and θ^d) for the inner one. The benefit of this inner control loop is to calculate corresponding thrusts for desired altitude and attitude, then given as control inputs for the system ($U_x, U_y, U_z, U_\phi, U_\theta, U_\psi$). The scheme in Figure 2 shows this control strategy.

Figure 2 Synoptic scheme of the adopted control system.

Based on the main approach explained in [7]-[8]-[9] the robust SMC was designed. (7) is the system equations of the six control laws generated for x, y, z displacement and roll, pitch and yaw angles.

where s is the SMC, λ and $\xi > 0$ coefficients of the SMC.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 U_x = \frac{m}{U_z} \left[\ddot{x}_1^d - \lambda_x \dot{e}_x - \xi_x s_1 - \mu_x \text{sign}(s_1) + \frac{k_{dx}}{m} x_2 \right] \\
 U_y = \frac{m}{U_z} \left[\ddot{x}_3^d - \lambda_y \dot{e}_y - \xi_y s_2 - \mu_y \text{sign}(s_2) + \frac{k_{dy}}{m} x_4 \right] \\
 U_z = \frac{m}{\cos \varphi \cos \theta} \left[\ddot{x}_5^d - \lambda_z \dot{e}_z - \xi_z s_3 - \mu_z \text{sign}(s_3) + \frac{k_{dz}}{m} x_6 + g \right] \\
 U_\varphi = I_x \left[\ddot{x}_7^d - \lambda_\varphi \dot{e}_\varphi - \xi_\varphi s_4 - \mu_\varphi \text{sign}(s_4) - \frac{(I_y - I_z)}{I_x} x_{10} x_{12} + \frac{k_{d\varphi}}{I_x} x_8^2 + \frac{I_r}{I_x} \bar{\Omega} x_{10} \right] \\
 U_\theta = I_y \left[\ddot{x}_9^d - \lambda_\theta \dot{e}_\theta - \xi_\theta s_5 - \mu_\theta \text{sign}(s_5) - \frac{(I_z - I_x)}{I_y} x_8 x_{12} + \frac{k_{d\theta}}{I_y} x_{10}^2 - \frac{I_r}{I_y} \bar{\Omega} x_8 \right] \\
 U_\psi = I_z \left[\ddot{x}_{11}^d - \lambda_\psi \dot{e}_\psi - \xi_\psi s_6 - \mu_\psi \text{sign}(s_6) - \frac{(I_x - I_y)}{I_z} x_8 x_{10} + \frac{k_{d\psi}}{I_z} x_{12}^2 \right]
 \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

A nonlinear control technique ‘‘Sliding Mode Control (SMC)’’ has been applied on a nonlinear model of the X4-flyer with the parameters given in table 1 [6].

Table 1 X4-flyer physical parameters.

Symbol	Value	Physical Significance
I_x	1.22	Quadrotor moment of inertia around X axis (Kg.m ²)
I_y	1.22	Quadrotor moment of inertia around Y axis (Kg.m ²)
I_z	2.2	Quadrotor moment of inertia around Z axis (Kg.m ²)
I_r	0.2	Total rotational moment of inertia around the rotor axis (Kg.m ²)
k_F	5	Lift factor (N/rad/s)
k_M	2	Drag factor (N.m/rad/s)
l	0.21	Arm length (m)
m	11	Total mass of the quadrotor (Kg)
g	9.806	Acceleration due to gravity (m/s ²)
k_{dx}	0.12	Translational drage coefficient according to X axes (N/m/s)
k_{dy}	0.12	Translational drage coefficient according to Y axes (N/m/s)
k_{dz}	0.12	Translational drage coefficient according to Z axes (N/m/s)
$k_{d\varphi}$	0.1	Rotational drage coefficient, Roll movement (N/rad/s)
$k_{d\theta}$	0.1	Rotational drage coefficient, Pitch movement (N/rad/s)
$k_{d\psi}$	0.1	Rotational drage coefficient, Yaw movement (N/rad/s)

Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6 represent the result of the application of the SMC on X4-flyer model. We can see that the system states track their desired values with errors close to zero.

Figure 3 trajectory tracking.

Figure 4 Position and attitude tracking.

Figure 5 Position and attitude errors.

Figure 6 Control Inputs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work deals with the control of an X4-flyer for the purpose of stabilizing the vehicle on its desired trajectory. Sliding mode controller was employed in both the position and attitude blocs. In order to further test the performance of the designed controller, the global system (quadrotor + controller) was used to simulate in MATLAB/Simulink.

In spite of the presence of chattering phenomena, we can see the good tracking of the desired trajectory. It is clearly shown that all the state variables converge to their reference values, even if these last are suddenly changed.

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